

TABLE 2 and Figs. 14 and 15 describe the requirements, concepts and processes of the battery recycling problem (UP1).

TABLE 1
ITEMS DEFINING THE UNFAMILIAR PROBLEM UP1

TYPE	ITEM ID	DESCRIPTION
Requirements	R1	The system will provide an option for manually starting up the separator.
	R2	The system will provide an option for automatically shutting down the separator when any of the three output bins contains a specified quantity of batteries.
	R3	The system will provide an option for manually starting up the shredder.
	R4	The system will provide an option for automatically shutting down the shredder when the output bin contains a specified quantity of battery powder.
	R5	The system will provide an option for manually starting up the crusher.
	R6	The system will provide an option for automatically shutting down the crusher when the output bin contains a specified quantity of battery powder.
	R7	The system will provide an option for manually starting up the distiller.
	R8	The system will provide an option for automatically shutting down the distiller when any of the output bins contains a specified quantity of metal.
	R9	The system will shut down the distiller when the distillation time has expired.
	R10	The system will provide an option for registering the corresponding recycling batch for the ash stored in each waste vat.
	R11	The system will provide an option for registering the delivery notes provided by the battery suppliers.
	R12	The system will provide an option for registering the allocated recycling batch for the batteries on each delivery note.
	R13	The system will provide an option for registering the collection notes provided by the vat transport suppliers.
	R14	The system will provide an option for registering the vats corresponding to each collection note.
	R15	The system will provide an option for registering the quantity of metals extracted by the recycling process.
Concepts	C1	Metal
	C2	Manganese
	C3	Mercury
	C4	Nickel
	C5	Cadmium
	C6	Copper
	C7	Zinc
	C8	Battery
	C9	General-purpose batteries
	C10	Button cells
	C11	Button cells containing manganese
	C12	Button cells not containing manganese
Concepts	C13	Supplier
	C14	Delivery note
	C15	Batch
	C16	Vat
	C17	Ash
	C18	Collection note

TYPE	ITEM ID	DESCRIPTION
	C19	Machine
	C20	Separator
	C21	Shredder
	C22	Distiller
	C23	Incinerator
	C24	Crusher
Processes	A1	Enter delivery note
	A2	Separate batteries
	A3	Crush button cells not containing manganese
	A4	Shred general-purpose batteries
	A5	Crush button cells containing manganese
	A6	Distil with steel
	A7	Distil without steel
	A8	Precipitate
	A9	Send message
	A10	Receive message
	A11	Send request
	A12	Receive request
	A13	Notify message reception
	A14	Execute deletion request
	A15	Close notification
	A16	Display message log (show message in chat)

UP1 – Activity Diagram

Fig. 1.

Activity diagram for unfamiliar problem — baseline experiment

UP1 - Concept Model

Fig. 2. Concept model of unfamiliar problem — baseline experiment